

**ASSESSMENT OF MANAGERIAL COMPETENCE OF DEPARTMENT HEADS IN
HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON R.S. NEMOV'S "LEADER"
METHODOLOGY**

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Annotation

This article explores the assessment of managerial competence in department heads of higher education institutions using R.S. Nemov's "Leader" methodology. The study focuses on identifying key leadership qualities and management skills, including responsibility, influence, and strategic thinking. The results highlight the importance of socio-psychological factors in shaping effective academic leadership.

Keywords: managerial competence, department head, higher education, R.S. Nemov, "Leader" methodology, leadership qualities, socio-psychological assessment, academic management.

In order to scientifically study the manifestation of managerial competence in department heads of higher education institutions, R.S. Nemov's "Leader" methodology was selected. This methodology allows for the identification of leadership qualities in individuals, including the ability to influence others in interpersonal relationships and the inclination to lead and inspire followers—key indicators of developed leadership and managerial traits. We considered it important to examine the potential differences in these qualities between male and female department heads working in various universities across the country. From this perspective, the methodology was administered to a selected group of participants, and the results were analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively by gender. The findings are presented in Table 1 and Figure 1.

Table 1

**Expression of Managerial Competence among Department Heads in Higher Education
Institutions by Gender (N=320)**
(Based on Student's t-test criterion)

Komponentlar	Kafedra mudirlari jinsi	N	O'rtacha qiymat	t	p
Boshqaruvchanlik sifatleri	Erkaklar	121	41,94	2,05	p≤0,05
	Ayollar	199	38,11		

According to the results presented in Table 1, when examining the manifestation of managerial qualities among department heads by gender, statistically significant differences were observed ($t = 2.05$; $p \leq 0.05$). These findings indicate that male department heads in higher education institutions are more likely than their female counterparts to consistently demonstrate a desire for leadership, a tendency to influence and guide others, a preference for taking control, and a lower inclination to feel subordinate to others. This pattern can be explained by psychological traits commonly found in men, such as a stronger drive for independence, higher motivation to achieve elevated status, greater emotional stability, and a reduced susceptibility to negative emotional experiences.

Figure 1. Gender-Based Representation of Managerial Competence Among Department Heads in Higher Education Institutions (N=320)

Based on the results presented above, it can be concluded that managerial qualities differ significantly by gender among the surveyed group. These differences are particularly evident in aspects such as influencing department members, guiding activities, and expressing leadership traits. This suggests that the emergence of leadership qualities in department heads working in higher education institutions is, in many cases, associated with gender-related factors.

In order to comprehensively examine the problem put forward in our dissertation, we aimed to identify the relationship between the managerial competence of department heads in higher education institutions and their tendencies toward conflict-prone behavior. This aspect was noted during the research as one of the key socio-psychological determinants. Therefore, we administered R.S. Nemov's "Leader" methodology and K.N. Thomas's "Conflict Behavior Tendency Diagnostics" questionnaire to selected respondent groups.

The conflict-related methodology consists of 30 questions and allows for the assessment of how individuals typically behave in various conflict situations. Through these tools, it becomes possible to determine how different forms of conflict behavior—namely, competition, collaboration, compromise, avoidance, and accommodation—affect the manifestation of managerial competence.

The data collected from the participants through these questionnaires were analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively, and the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

The Relationship Between Managerial Competence and Conflict Behavior Styles Among Department Heads in Higher Education Institutions (N=320)
(Based on Pearson Correlation Criterion)

Conflict Behavior Styles	Male Department Heads	Female Department Heads
Competition	-0.55**	-0.34*
Collaboration	0.31*	0.18*
Compromise	-0.05	0.27*
Avoidance	-0.19*	0.03
Accommodation	-0.01	0.12

Note: * – $p \leq 0.05$; ** – $p \leq 0.01$

According to the results of the administered methodology (see Table 2), a significant negative correlation was observed between managerial qualities and the use of the competition style among male department heads working in higher education institutions ($r = -0.55$; $p \leq 0.01$). This finding suggests that in unexpected or unpleasant situations that arise during work, behaviors such as reacting aggressively toward the source of the issue, being unwilling to withdraw from arguments, and expressing opinions in a harsh manner can hinder the positive development and manifestation of managerial qualities.

Furthermore, an increase in behaviors such as avoiding conflict in interpersonal relationships during professional activities, responding to differing opinions with composure, and striving to resolve disputes constructively can contribute to the further development of managerial competence among department heads.

Among male respondents, a positive correlation was observed between managerial qualities and the collaboration style ($r = 0.31$; $p \leq 0.05$). These results highlight that the more developed the qualities of making rational decisions in complex and conflict-prone situations, analyzing others' viewpoints, and striving to maintain positive interactions with colleagues, the more likely it is that managerial competence is well-formed in department heads.

Additionally, in conflict situations that arise unexpectedly during the work process, behaviors such as showing respect for the interests of others, avoiding escalation, striving for resolution, being attentive to the emotional states of interlocutors, and attempting to resolve issues constructively contribute to the development of managerial qualities among male department heads.

Additionally, it was found that among male department heads working in higher education institutions, managerial qualities were significantly negatively correlated with the avoidance conflict behavior style ($r = -0.19$; $p \leq 0.05$). These findings suggest that as managerial competencies increase, the tendency to avoid disagreements, refrain from engaging in disputes, and avoid asserting one's interests in conflict or problematic situations tends to decrease.

Furthermore, in complex situations that arise during professional activity, the growth of traits such as assertiveness and a willingness to resolve problems contributes positively to the development of managerial qualities.

References

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